

MULTIBODY SIMULATIONS WITH REDUCED ORDER FLEXIBLE BODIES OBTAINED BY FEA

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APPENDIX

The following sections are part of the manuscript working files for the corresponding MEDSI 2020 paper [1]. For sake of brevity they were removed from the original paper but are supplied as additional information material for the better understanding of the reduction procedure. We hope to enable others in this way to use this method for their purpose.

This file is permanently stored¹. In addition, we provide useful APDL code snippets.

ANNEX A: SUPERELEMENT THEORY

The aim of this appendix is to clarify how the generation of a reduced order flexible body from a FEA model works in theory. This is explained starting from a discrete finite element model.

It is important to note that the explained reduction methods are executed almost automatically by a suitable FEA software after the required user input. The theoretical background is rather given for the proper understanding of typical discrete system background.

Explications are based on the cited original papers as well as the ANSYS help [2, 3]. Mathematical notation is orientated on the ANSYS notation, e.g. \mathbf{K}_{ms} referring to a sub-matrix of the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} with dimensions of m rows (number of chosen retained master DoFs) and s columns (number of not-retained slave DoFs of the FEA model).

A typical transient-dynamic FEA model solves the discrete dynamic equation of motion

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F} \quad (1)$$

for a system without damping, where \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} denote the global mass and stiffness matrix respectively. These are typically assembled by a FEA solver. For n DoFs of the FEA model the global system matrices $\mathbf{K}_{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{M}_{n \times n}$ are thus of size $n \times n$.

The aim of the order reduction is to reduce this full set of n DoFs of the full FEA model (typically $n > 100,000$) to a chosen subset of m (typically $m < 100$) retained so called “master” DoFs and s dropped “slave” DoFs. This leads to

$$m = n - s \quad (2)$$

retained DoFs. For that matter the global matrices are reorganized such that eq. (1) becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{mm} & \mathbf{M}_{ms} \\ \mathbf{M}_{sm} & \mathbf{M}_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_m \\ \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_s \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{mm} & \mathbf{K}_{ms} \\ \mathbf{K}_{sm} & \mathbf{K}_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_m \\ \mathbf{u}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_m \\ \mathbf{F}_s \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The reduction of the global matrices \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} is performed with help of transformation matrix \mathbf{T} via

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{T}, \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}} = \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{T}, \quad (5)$$

which leads to the reduced order system matrices $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ of drastically reduced size compared to \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} .

Depending on the chosen reduction technique, the transformation matrix \mathbf{T} can have different shapes and content. *Simscape* only supports flexible body reduced order models obtained with the “fixed-interface” method, also “Craig-Bampton-method” [4, 5]. ANSYS also permits the FEA reduction of components with this method. For the “Craig-Bampton-method” the transformation matrix takes the form

$$\mathbf{T}_{(m+p) \times (m+p)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{G}_{sm} & \Phi_{sp} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{I} denotes the identity matrix of dimension $m \times m$. The sub-matrix

$$\mathbf{G}_{sm} = -\mathbf{K}_{ss}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{sm} \quad (7)$$

is only derived from sub-matrices of the global stiffness matrix.

The particularity of $\mathbf{T}_{(m+p) \times (m+p)}$ is the sub-matrix Φ_{sp} that contains a user-chosen number of p Eigenvectors of s rows. These Eigenvalues are the result of the Eigenvalue problem

$$\omega^2 \mathbf{M}_{ss} \phi_s = \mathbf{K}_{ss} \phi_s \quad (8)$$

of the constrained substructure (only containing the s “slave” DoFs) with blocked “master” DoFs. Thus the name of the method: “fixed-interface” method. The chosen subset of p pairs of Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors is done by the user, usually to assure representation of the reduced part’s modal behaviour up to a certain Eigenfrequency under fixed interface DoFs.

This leads to p additionally retained modes in the reduced model to the m retained “master” DoFs (eq. 2). To be precise the fixed-interface method creates thus a reduced order model of $m + p$ retained DoFs and modes. The DoFs in p are non-physical generalized coordinates that are not further explained here but help to represent the dynamic behaviour of the reduced component to additional higher frequencies.

The presented method is one possibility for the so-called “modal reduction” or component mode synthesis (CMS). This name refers to the synthesis of the dynamic modal behaviour of a relatively big discrete model to a subset of selected interface “master” DoFs and additional Eigenvalues/vectors.

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Figure 1: Meshed FEA model of an amplified piezo. Number of nodes: $\approx 130\,000$.

ANNEX B: REDUCTION PROCEDURE IN PRACTICE

Multibody models

To properly design the previously discussed end-station hexapod in terms of its dynamic transient performance, we chose a multibody model approach. This enables us to do perform simulations quite rapidly in sub-ms time-step resolution as it consists of a relatively small amount of degrees of freedom (DoFs).

Performing the modal reduction on FEA components and thus reducing the number of DoFs of the component enables us to consider its flexible behaviour in multibody models that are foreseen for a smaller number of DoFs.

FEA

FEA models are a suitable method to gain information on the modal dynamic behaviour of mechanical components or assemblies. Such models are usually used to obtain for example resonance frequencies of sensitive components of a new design.

Typically a FEA solver obtains these Eigenfrequencies ω and corresponding Eigenvectors ϕ from an Eigenvalue problem via the Stiffness K and Mass matrix M of the discretized full model:

$$\omega^2 M \phi = K \phi. \quad (9)$$

The intermediate assembly of these *global matrices* can be exploited to gain information on the stiffness and inertia relations within the components. However, the corresponding matrices in eq. (9) are for the full set of n DoFs of the FEA model. This yields square matrices $K_{n \times n}$ and $M_{n \times n}$ both of size $n \times n$. This is usually of relatively big number compared to the small numbers of multibody mechatronics models ($n > 100\,000$). This is illustrated with the meshed 3D-FEA model of an APA in Fig. 1. Each of the nodes has 3 DoFs, leading to some $n \approx 400\,000$ DoFs for the full model.

To reduce the number of DoFs of the FEA models one can use modal reduction techniques, which are explained further below.

Figure 2: Nano end-station and a detailed view of one of its 6 legs consisting of an amplified piezoelectric actuator (APA) and two flexible joints.

Combining multibody models and FEA

The extraction of relevant stiffness and inertia relations for flexible elements (e.g. flexure joints, thin plates) via FEA can be a great advantage to consider these element's modal behaviour in multibody models if their resonances might limit the system performances.

Since recently the modelling of flexible bodies is possible with the *Simscape* multibody software [5, 6]. This models a deformable body of arbitrary geometry based on a reduced order model. A reduced-order model is “a computationally efficient model that characterizes the mechanical properties of a flexible body under small deformations.” Computational efficiency results from the drastically reduced number of degrees of freedom of the concerned body compared to a classic meshed body for FEA (often several hundreds of DoFs). Basic data required to model a body in such way in *Simscape* is:

- A list of coordinates of coordinates that represent the flexible body's interface frames or nodes,
- A *reduced* symmetric stiffness matrix \hat{K} describing elastic properties of the component,
- A *reduced* symmetric mass matrix \hat{M} describing inertial properties of the component.

The latter matrices can be derived from FEA models of arbitrary continuous bodies with typical FEA software packages, which is explained in the next subsections for the *ANSYS Mechanical* package. This method is then applied to an amplified piezo actuator of the NASS.

Modal reduction

We used the modal reduction (also component mode synthesis, CMS) technique to obtain the previously discussed reduced order models of the hexapod legs shown in Fig. 2b as an input for our *Simscape* model. More specifically we used the fixed-interface method, also called “Craig-Bampton-method” [4] and applied this method to the FEA model of the amplified piezo.

We give a compiled theoretical explanation how the fixed-interface method works in the Annex A. This should help the

readers understand how the FEA solver performs the modal reduction to generate the reduced order models. This leads to a significantly reduced number of $m + p$ DoFs of the reduced order model with m retained master DoFs (or interface DoFs, usually some 10s) and p additionally retained Eigenmodes (usually a few additional).

Reduction procedure in practice

The above described procedure is easiest done in practice with a FEA software package. We used ANSYS for this matter and followed the developed procedure represented in Fig. 3. This schema illustrates the different steps we followed to create a reduced order model (or superelement in FEA terms) from our existing CAD files of concerned parts. The steps can generally split into

1. Geometry preparation,
2. Generation pass,
3. Matrix writing.

Geometry preparation We import the CAD file in the ANSYS SpaceClaim geometry editor for simplification. This geometry is imported in the ANSYS Mechanical GUI. We used “remote points” on interface geometries (faces/edges) that we wanted to retain as an *interface frame* of the reduced order model. This creates a multi-point-constraint between all DoFs of the chosen geometry and averages their displacements into translational and rotational DoFs. Point masses can also be added to add inertia to the reduced part.

Generation pass For the generation pass 2 modules can be used: either continuing with ANSYS Mechanical or using the old Mechanical APDL GUI. In the more recent Mechanical the part is reduced with the “condensed geometry” options, which limits the reduction techniques to the previously explained CMS/“Craig-Bampton-method”. This generates a ANSYS native binary *.sub file that contains the generated substructure (mass, stiffness) information. The coordinates of the retained interface points need to be written during this process to be able to read them with Simscape for later use. For the use of ANSYS Mechanical we attached a useful script in Annex C.

Matrix writing We used an ANSYS APDL script to transform the generated *.sub file into readable file formats. The commands *DMAT and *EXPORT are here the most relevant commands to first load the *.SUB file into an APDL matrix variable and then export this into readable format. An example script is shown in Annex C.

ANNEX C: USEFUL APDL CODES

In this appendix we show some useful ANSYS APDL code scripts that can help during the modal reduction procedure.

Remark: Comment lines are marked by an “!” in APDL.

Code 1: Export of Interface DoF coordinates

The code snippet in Listing 1 can be used before the modal reduction on the model just prior to the SOLVE command. If ANSYS Mechanical is used, this snippet can be inserted below the “condensed geometry” item in the tree, as shown in Fig. 4.

Listing 1: Command snippet to export nodal coordinates of selected master DoF nodes. Also provided as file: APDL-codes/write_MDoFs.mac

```
! Write Output to txt file
/OUTPUT,out_nodes_3D,txt,c:/ANSYS_temp

! Get maximum node number in model
*GET,max_node,NODE,0,NUM,MAX,

! Select only master nodes
NSEL,S,M,,1,max_node

! List node coordinates for output, then
  reselect original set
NLIST
NSEL,ALL

! List master nodes and corresponding selected
  DoFs
MLIST
! Re-direct output to terminal
/OUTPUT,TERM
```

Code 2: Export of ANSYS Matrices as *.csv files

The code in Listing 2 can be used in an ANSYS Mechanical APDL instance to convert binary ANSYS matrix data to readable *.csv format (here exponential format with precision 16). The variable ARG1 needs to be replaced by the *.sub substructure file.

Listing 2: APDL macro to convert *.sub binary substructure files to readable *.csv files. Also provided as file: APDL-codes/write_mats.mac

```
! Create Matrices K (stiffness) and M (mass)
  from file specified as 'ARG1'
*DMAT,mat_K,,IMPORT,SUB,ARG1,STIFF
*DMAT,mat_M,,IMPORT,SUB,ARG1,MASS

! Print matrices to a csv file with specified
  precision (exponential format)
*EXPORT,mat_K,CSV,mat_K.CSV,16
*EXPORT,mat_M,CSV,mat_M.CSV,16
```

REFERENCES

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Figure 3: Procedure that was followed for the order reduction of finite element models.

Figure 4: Command snipped position in condensed geometry to export coordinates.

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